

	total	female	male	unknown	Chi- Quadrat
Question 4					p=0,134
Scar 1	161/327 (49,2%)	66 (41.8)	78 (56.1)	17 (56.7)	
Scar 2	26/327 (8,0%)	16 (10.1)	7 (5.0)	3 (10.0)	
Scar 3	139/327 (42,5%)	76 (48.1)	53 (38,1)	10 (33.3)	
none	1/327 (0,3%)	0	1 (0.7)	0	
Question 5					p=0,411
Scar 1	58/327 (17,7%)	29 (18.4)	22 (15.8)	7 (23.3)	
Scar 2	150/327 (45,9%)	76 (48.1)	66 (47.5)	8 (26.7)	
Scar 3	109/327 (33,3%)	49 (31.0)	47 (33.8)	13 (43.3)	
none	10/327 (3,1%)	4 (2.5)	4 (2.9)	2 (6.7)	
Question 6					p=0,011
Scar 1	60/327 (18,3%)	31 (19.6)	21 (15.1)	8 (26.7)	
Scar 2	165/327 (50,5%)	85 (53.8)	69 (49.6)	11 (36.7)	
Scar 3	88/327 (26,9%)	34 (21.5)	47 (33.8)	7 (23.3)	
none	14/327 (4,3%)	8 (5.1)	2 (1.4)	4 (13.3)	
Question 7					p=0,009
Scar 1	138/327 (42,2%)	52 (32.9)	69 (49.6)	17 (56.7)	
Scar 2	24/327 (7,3%)	10 (6.3)	11 (7.9)	3 (10.0)	
Scar 3	147/327 (45,0%)	89 (56.3)	50 (36.0)	8 (26.7)	
none	18/327 (5,5%)	7 (4.4)	9 (6.5)	2 (6.7)	
Question 8					p=0,346
Scar 1	67/327 (20,5%)	36 (22.8)	26 (18.7)	5 (16.7)	
Scar 2	154/327 (47,1%)	80 (50.6)	63 (45.3)	11 (36.7)	
Scar 3	89/327 (27,2%)	35 (22.2)	43 (30.9)	11 (36.7)	
none	17/327 (5,2%)	7 (4.4)	7 (5.0)	3 (10.0)	
Question 9					p=0,001
Scar 1	84/327 (25,7%)	57 (36.1)	20 (14.4)	7 (23.3)	
Scar 2	136/327 (41,6%)	50 (31.6)	73 (52.5)	13 (43.3)	
Scar 3	95/327 (29,1%)	46 (29.1)	41 (29.5)	8 (26.7)	
none	12/327 (4,1,7%)	5 (3.2)	5 (3.6)	2 (6.7)	
Question 10					p=0,497
Scar 1	53/327 (13,2%)	28 (17.7)	22 (15.8)	3 (10.0)	

Scar 2	164/327 (50,2%)	84 (53.2)	68 (48.9)	12 (40.0)	
Scar 3	96/327 (29,4%)	40 (25.3)	43 (30.9)	13 (43.3)	
none	14/327 (4,3%)	6 (3.8)	6 (4.3)	2 (6.7)	
Question 11					p=0,057
Scar 1	144/327 (44,0%)	55 (34.8)	73 (52.5)	16 (53.3)	
Scar 2	26/327 (8,0%)	12 (7.6)	11 (7.9)	3 (10.0)	
Scar 3	155/327 (47,4%)	90 (57.0)	54 (38.9)	11 (36.7)	
none	2/327 (0,6%)	1 (0.6)	1 (0.7)	0	
Question 12					p=0,005
Scar 1	134/327 (41,0%)	49 (31.0)	72 (51.8)	13 (43.3)	
Scar 2	21/327 (6,4%)	9 (5.7)	11 (7.9)	1 (3.3)	
Scar 3	168/327 (51,4%)	99 (62.7)	54 (38.8)	15 (50.0)	
none	4/327 (1,2%)	1 (0.6)	2 (1.4)	1 (3.3)	
Question 13					p=0,069
Scar 1	50/327 (15,3%)	31 (19.6)	16 (11.5)	3 (10.0)	
Scar 2	181/327 (55,4%)	90 (57.0)	74 (53.2)	17 (56.7)	
Scar 3	73/327 (22,3%)	24 (15.2)	41 (29.5)	8 (26.7)	
none	23/327 (7,0%)	13 (8.2)	8 (5.8)	2 (6.7)	
Question 14					p=0,094
Scar 1	46/327 (14,1%)	29 (18.4)	11 (7.9)	6 (20.0)	
Scar 2	151/327 (46,2%)	76 (48.1)	62 (44.6)	13 (43.3)	
Scar 3	62/327 (19,0%)	24 (15.2)	32 (23.0)	6 (20.0)	
none	68/327 (20,8%)	29 (18.4)	34 (24.5)	5 (16.7)	